

***Tarchonanthus
camphoratus***
Camphor bush

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 2 – 9 metres in height.

Distribution:

Tarchonanthus camphoratus occurs across several provinces in South Africa, including Limpopo, North West, Gauteng, Mpumalanga, the Free State and the Northern Cape.

Importance:

The camphor bush is valued for its medicinal properties, including reported antioxidant activity. Its genome assembly provides a useful resource for future research into the genetic basis of its medicinal and ecological traits.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 143.62 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 10.78 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 3.83 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.1% [Single: 3.0%, Duplicated: 96.1%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 12 814.9 kilobases

Contig number: 2 277

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